

Article

Kinetics study on the H₂ reduction of Nchwanning manganese ore at elevated temperatures

Authors:

- **Alok Sarkar** – NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Resources, Energy & Environment research group.
- **Trygve Lindahl Schanche** – SINTEF Industry, Trondheim, Norway.
- **Maria Wallin** – NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Resources, Energy & Environment research group.
- **Jafar Safarian** – NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Resources, Energy & Environment research group.

Read full article

[DOI: 10.1007/s12613-025-3094-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12613-025-3094-x)

Co-funded by
the European Union